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D3.7 – Policies and Datasets Catalogue V1

(Version 1.0, 11/11/2022)

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1	GFT ITALIA SRL	GFT	Italy		
2	STICHTING EGI	EGI	Netherlands		
3	NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT	INTRA	Luxembourg		
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6	UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA	UNP	Portugal		
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Abbreviations

DL	Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
ICT	Information and communication technologies
ML	Machine Learning
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable describes the development of the AI4PublicPolicy Dataset and Policies Catalogue, which is based on the UNPARALLEL Web Framework. The catalogue defines a data model required for the representation of datasets, which includes different types of data that can be represented, different types of measurements including their units, datasets with collected data and the information where and how the data is collected. The data stored using this model will be provided through public and private access through two endpoints, a web interface where the information will be provided through several web pages (private access will be authenticated through username and password) and a Rest API which will enable external applications and modules to consult, add and edit information regarding the datasets, in which case authentication is provided through a revocable token.

The deliverable presents detailed information about both endpoints, the web interface, i.e., the pages and visual elements that have been developed including a list of used frontend technologies, and regarding the available Rest API communication features and also a schema with all the accesses provided by this endpoint.

This document is a first version of the result of Task 3.5, and later in the project a 2nd (and final) version of this deliverable will be submitted with all the details of the implementation of the final version of the AI4PublicPolicy catalogue of policies and datasets.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e., AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of WP3

WP3 “AI-based Reusable and Interoperable Policies” is a central work package in the AI4PublicPolicy platform. This work package provides the necessary components for: 1) enabling data collection and management of different types of datasets 2) Make data usable through

interoperability techniques. 3) Enable reuse of datasets, policies, and AI models. 3) Contribute to openness through an open catalogue of policies, datasets and AI models.

1.3 Objective of the Deliverable

The main objective of this deliverable is to provide a first version of the Policies and Datasets Catalogue, the outcome of Task 3.5 – Searchable Catalogue of Policies and Datasets.

The task aims to provide a searchable catalogue of policies and datasets in the form of a registry. Through this task access to policies and data will be made available for analysis, usage and implementation in various situations. Through the provision of such a registry the AI tools to analyse data will always be only a click away, which will make it faster for public administrators to create policies using the registered data. The catalogue will enable easy access and increased searchability to the stakeholders, by providing an adaptable search engine that will offer semantic AI models that will create semantic links among the different keywords, for identifying the fingerprint of the searched policy or dataset and providing in real-time the requested result.

This 1st version of the deliverable is focused on the datasets of AI4PublicPolicy, and the way the catalogue is meant to represent this information. The next steps of the task will be dedicated to the visual representation of the AI4PublicPolicy policies.

1.4 Structure of the Deliverable

This document is structured as follows:

- **Objective of the Catalogue of Policies and Datasets (Section 2):** The Catalogue development followed a well-defined goal, and every decision and implementation were made to meet it.
- **Background Technology (Section 3):** A catalogue of this complexity, is to not be done from scratch. It is important to define which technology will be used and serve as a baseline for development.
 - **UNPARALLEL Web Framework (sub-section 3.1):** The task leader UNP, which is leading the development of the catalogue will base it on its existing technologies, thus expanding its UNPARALLEL Web Framework to support Datasets and Policies.
- **AI4PublicPolicy Dataset Catalogue (Section 4):** The main result of this work is this catalogue. This section focuses on the Catalogue internals, and what was developed to make it a reality.
 - **Data Representation:** A Catalogue consisting of all the relating information easily accessed and searchable.
 - **Endpoints:** A catalogue must have well defined points of access. This one can be accessed in the following two ways:
 - **Web Interface:** In order to provide easy access to humans, a web interface was designed.
 - **Rest API:** A Rest API was designed to facilitate direct access to the information and to offer integration in the architecture and with the rest of the modules.
- **Roadmap (Section 5):** This section focuses on the development lifecycle of the AI4PublicPolicy Catalogue component.

2 Objective of the Catalogue of Policies and Datasets

The Catalogue for Policies & Datasets is a component which will list all Policies and Datasets related to AI4PublicPolicy. All information pertinent to the execution of the project will be made available through this component, and thus providing policy makers access to the already available policies and datasets.

Apart from the increased searchability, the catalogue will provide more knowledge base functionalities for comparison and recommendation of datasets and/or policies. By modelling datasets and policies, along with associated metadata, the catalogue can offer some decision support system functionalities, such as recommendation of related datasets or policies. This can be accomplished using a “similarity rank”, and when a user accesses a specific entry in the catalogue, it will also receive information about related datasets and/or policies.

3 Background Technology

This section describes the usage of UNPARALLEL Web Framework, a well-established framework, which is the outcome of several developments from UNPARALLEL Innovations from the past years.

1.1 UNPARALLEL Web Framework

Figure 2. UNPARALLEL Web Framework

The UNPARALLEL Web framework, with its established way of structuring content and since it has already been used in company products (such as the IoT-Catalogue.com) was the perfect candidate to leverage the content of the Catalogue for Policies & Datasets. UNPARALLEL Web framework serves as a backend base of information, providing the Catalogue for Policies & Datasets with data on components and validations as well as dataset and policies developed on this project through the following functionalities:

i) **Product's Inventory**

Provides information about several components from simple sensors with more simple function to more complex products delivering out-of-the-box technological solutions, with the possibility to apply filters when listing the products, by type, by where was used, etc.

When opening a product, more detailed information is displayed to the user, including its characteristics, where it is available for purchase, price, name, description, etc. Several interactive bars are provided allowing an intuitive way for the user to navigate within the product and through the other elements related with the product.

ii) ICT Problems and Value Propositions Directory

This framework provides a way to describe several situations which could be described as a simple technological problem known as an ICT Problem. It usually describes a very simple situation (ex: Measure Temperature) that can make use of several products to provide a solution (ex: Temperature sensor).

A Value Proposition should be used when describing more complex problems, with usually reduced focus on the technological part and an increased focus on the type of problem to be solved. For instance: to describe how to solve a value proposition for a client or a partner, we should break it into ICT Problems and then indicate which products we should use to solve each one.

iii) Use Case's Explorer

A use case defines a real world scenario which could be an experiment, process or other type of activity. The UNPARALLEL Web Framework gives an extensive support to define an use case, which will be characterized by Value Propositions, ICT Problems, Products and solutions, making this framework a powerful tool for anyone who wants to define a real world complex scenario that can be solved by solutions relying on products available on the market.

iv) Usage in IoT-Catalogue.com

Figure 3. IoT Catalogue Logo

Our IoT-catalogue.com application makes extensive use of the UNPARALLEL Web Framework to provide information related with IoT, including several technological products and its applicability on use cases which are part of several EU Research projects. This application is used by partners working on EU Research projects, as it provides an organized way to consult the information about a project where they are working and find other projects sharing the same solutions and products, enabling the creation of connections between partners of different projects.

So far IoT Catalogue was used or is still being used in the following projects: Boost 4.0, FAR-EDGE, ICP4Life, IoF2020, KYKLOS 4.0, MONICA, PROPHECY, Qu4lity, Thomas, VICINITY and WAZIUP this last project already finished was the first being included on IoT-Catalogue.com.

4 AI4PublicPolicy Dataset Catalogue

AI4PublicPolicy Dataset Catalogue is powered by UNPARALLEL Web Framework and enables the support for modelling and storing data about the AI4publicPolicy Datasets, the data which is stored on a DB can be added, edited and obtained by the user through several web interfaces and by external applications using the Rest API's provided by a Rest Server.

Figure 4. Catalogue endpoints

4.1 Data Representation

AI4PublicPolicy Dataset Catalogue data support provides features to enable the modelling and usage of different data concepts, measurement types and data values, including data integration with components and validations.

The following diagram defines how data is represented and how it relates to validations and components available on AI4PublicPolicy Dataset Catalogue.

Figure 5. Data Representation Diagram

Schema

The schema (model representation) is the specification issued by an official entity used to describe units and different types of measurements, a given measurable quantity or unit could have several schemas describing its usage under different purposes.

Unit

Unit used on a given measurement, this value includes its name, symbol and schema associated with the Unit.

Measurable Quantity

Specification of a measurement type, including a description of what is measured and the units that are supported, pairs of Measurable Quantity – Unit can be included on validations, components, data concepts and datasets allowing build relations between different types of data and different data elements on AI4PP Dataset catalogue giving a broader view where the data is being used.

Data Concept

Specification of a broader group including a list of possible measurements which are part of the same family. For example, considering the data concept “Weather Data” the main goal is to measure information regarding the atmospheric conditions, regarding past measurements and weather predictions.

A data concept contains pairs of Measurable Quantity – Unit supported and regarding Weather Data is possible to find different measurement types for several atmospheric conditions including its units (such as Temperature – Celsius degrees).

Dataset

Contains information about data collected which is part of a specific data concept and defined within a validation, the collection happens at a geographical location during a specific period in time.

The Dataset values are collected by a component (ex: sensor) using a specific Measurable Quantity and unit, the data values are defined in a data source through an URL or a file.

4.2 Endpoints

The data described above is stored in the AI4PublicPolicy Dataset Catalogue and could be accessed by a user through a web interface or by an external application using a rest API. Both access methods provide authentication for private data access.

Catalogue Rest API 1.0.0 OAS3

Used to enable the communication between the catalogue and external services, a token could be required when accessing restricted information. The Rest API uses JSON for the communication between an external service and the catalogue, providing the following features:

- **Token authentication:** For private accesses an authorized user could be authenticated using an unique token, the token could be revoked to remove the user permission.
- **Data fetching:** Allows an external application to fetch private (when provided a token) and public data.
- **Data Search:** Returns search results based on a query, some wild card like "" could be used.
- **Data update:** Used to update data available on IoT Catalogue, this feature could be useful in scenarios where the data must be updated on a regular basis, a token is required to use this feature.
- **Adding new data:** Used to insert new data on Catalogue, useful when adding large sets of data, a token is required to use this feature.

[Terms of service](#)

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Authorize

Catalogue API Get, search, add, edit and remove data from IoT Catalogue

[Find out more](#)

GET	/getData/{elementId}	Returns a data element	
GET	/getDataList/{elementId}	Get a list of data elements	
POST	/editDataElement	Edit an existing data element	
POST	/addNewData	Add a new data element	
GET	/searchData	Returns a list of data elements based on a search queryo Input	
DELETE	/deleteDataElement/{elementId}	Delete a data element	

Figure 6. Datasets Catalogue Swagger REST API

4.2.1 Web Interface

It allows the interaction with several web components containing data on the catalogue. A username/ password is required when accessing restricted information. This interface is developed using the latest frontend technologies including:

- **React:** A JavaScript library which allows the creation of reusable UI components used for building single page applications.
- **Bootstrap:** Library with visual elements used to build responsive web interfaces.
- **Meteor:** Full-stack framework used to build web apps based in JavaScript.
- **Distributed Data Protocol:** Proprietary Meteor protocol based on web sockets allowing real-time communication between the front-end and back-end.

Each page on the catalogue provides a different web interface which is composed of several web components relevant to the topic of the page.

As for data representation the following pages will be developed:

Data concept page

This page shows information about a data concept including its name, description and several interactive bars, providing further information and relations with measurable quantities, components and datasets.

Weather Data

Provide information about the weather and climate of a region. It tracks patterns and predicts trends. Weather refers to short-term atmospheric conditions of a region and can include indicators such as minimum/ maximum temperature, humidity, or wind speed. Climate is the weather of a region averaged over a long period of time. Climate data covers details such as seasonal average temperatures or decade-long patterns of rains and contributes to climate prediction.

Measurable Quantities

8 Quantities ^

Quantity	Description	Unit
Wind intensity	Wind intensity recorded at 10 meters high	km/h
Temperature	Temperature recorded at 1.5 meters high, hourly average	°C
Solar radiation	Solar radiation	kJ/m ²
Wind direction	Wind direction class to the prevailing wind direction recorded at 10 meters high	°
Precipitation	Precipitation recorded at a height of 1.5 meters, accumulated hourly value	mm
Wind intensity	Wind intensity recorded at 10 meters high	m/s
Humidity	Humidity recorded at 1.5 meters high, hourly average	%
Atmospheric pressure	Atmospheric pressure, reduced to mean sea level (NMM), hourly average	hPa

Used on

1 Use Case 1 Product ^

IPMA Weather Data Service

Solution capable of reading real-time data typical of a weather station, using different sensors...

API

Use Cases
Product

Datasets

2 Datasets ^

Wind and Precipitation data collection

Duration: 17 Oct 2022 to 18 Oct 2022

Precipitation
Wind direction
Wind intensity

Temperature and humidity data collecti...

Duration: 17 Oct 2022 to 18 Oct 2022

Air temperature
Relative air humidity

Figure 7. Data Concept page

Measurable Quantities

List which helps to characterize the data concept by giving a list of measurable quantities and units supported, considering the “Weather Data” concept example, all the measurable quantities will be related with weather predictions and measurements.

Used On

This bar shows all the products and use cases that were used or can be used to obtain data relevant to this data concept. Clicking on a product or use case will open a component page allowing the user to see more detailed information.

Datasets

List view of datasets containing information about all data collections related with this data concept, including the name, time period and measurable quantity names.

This bar (on the top right) provides a button to enable the map view mode allowing to show the data concept datasets in a more detailed way including, its values, locations, etc.

Dataset map view

This map view provides an interactive overview of all Datasets locations.

Figure 8. Interactive map view

The view provides a dataset clickable listing using cards and geographical points, selecting a dataset will show on the right area of the view detailed information about the dataset including last measurements, usage on use cases and devices used.

4.2.2 Rest API

Used to enable the communication between the catalogue and external services, a token could be required when accessing restricted information.

The Rest API uses JSON for the communication between an external service and the catalogue, providing the following features:

- **Token authentication:** For private accesses an authorized user could be authenticated using a unique token, the token could be revoked to remove the user permission.
- **Data fetching:** Allows an external application to fetch private (when a token is provided) and public data.
- **Data Search:** Returns search results based on a query. Some wild card like "*" could be used.
- **Data update:** Used to update data available on IoT Catalogue, this feature could be useful in scenarios where the data must be updated on a regular basis. A token will be required to use this feature.
- **Adding new data:** Used to insert new data on Catalogue. It is particularly useful when adding large sets of data. A token will be required to use this feature.

The following endpoints provide access to methods to manipulate information. All the API responses are in JSON format.

- **getData:** Returns a data element.
 - **Input:**
 - **16atatype:** Type of data (validation, dataset, dataConcept, etc.)
 - **id:** Id of the data element
 - **access_token:** Required when fetching private data
 - **Output:**
 - Data element in JSON format
- **getDataList:** Returns a list of data elements
 - **Input:**
 - **16atatype:** Type of data
 - **limit:** Maximum number of results to be returned
 - **skip:** When is necessary to skip a certain number of results
 - **access_token:** Required when fetching private data
 - **filter:** Mongo JSON filter object
 - **sort:** Mongo JSON sort object
 - **Output:**
 - Data concept in JSON format
- **editData:** Edit an existing data element
 - **Input:**
 - **16atatype:** Type of data
 - **id:** Id of the data element
 - **data:** JSON Containing the updates
 - **access_token:** Required for authentication
 - **Output:**
 - JSON Object with fail or success message
- **addNewData:** Add a new data element

- **Input:**
 - **17atatype:** Type of data
 - **data:** JSON Containing the new data element
 - **access_token:** Required for authentication
- **Output:**
 - JSON Object with fail or success message
- **searchData:** Returns a list of data elements based on a search query
 - **Input:**
 - **17atatype:** Type of data
 - **searchQuery:** JSON Containing the search query
 - **access_token:** Required when searching private data
 - **Output:**
 - JSON Object with fail or success message

5 Roadmap

The AI4PublicPolicy Catalogue development focuses on a strict plan of development and usage. On the development side, the focus is on making an incremental approach, to have fully stable and complete versions available while adding new functionalities to the Catalogue. On the usage side, this catalogue is to be used by the pilots directly and to make the information publicly available within the AI4PublicPolicy marketplace.

The Development lifecycle is focused in three stages:

1. AI4PublicPolicy Datasets Catalogue: this is the first iteration, which demonstrates the full development of the dataset support on the catalogue, including web interfaces and endpoints for other modules to use.
2. Marketplace Integration: the second stage is the development of the integration of this catalogue with the project marketplace, giving access to project results to the community.
3. AI4PublicPolicy Policy Catalogue: the last step is the development of support for cataloguing the policies.